

A study on plant nutrition balance, soil fertility and economic returns of investments

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Original Research Article Received on March 18, 2020 Revised on March 26, 2020 Accepted on April 12, 2020 Published on April 20, 2020</p> <p>Article Author Attia El Gayar</p> <p>Corresponding Author Email attiaelgayar@yahoo.com</p>	<p>Plant nutrition balance plays a major role in the universal need to increase food production to meet the demands of the growing world population. Fertilizer application resulted in marked crop yield increases, which for most crops were more than hundred. The extent to which fertilizers are used still differs considerably between various regions of the world. Soil nutrient status is widely constrained by the limited use of inorganic and organic fertilizers and by nutrient loss mainly due to erosion and leaching. Many small holder farmers do not have access to synthetic fertilizer because of high price of fertilizers, lack of credit facilities, poor distribution, and other socio-economic factors. Consequently, crop yields are low, in fact decreasing in many areas, and the sustainability of the current farming system is at risk. Therefore, the aim of this review was to review the role of integrated Plant nutrition balance management for improving crop yield and enhancing soil fertility under small holder farmers in dry areas, and recommend the appropriate approaches for enhancing soil fertility and increasing crop yield for small holder farmers in dry and semi-dry areas. These are the key challenges of adoption in the scaling up of such alternative soil fertility management practices to millions of small-scale farmers. There is a need, therefore, for research and extension to sort out issues of adoption and scaling up of the available options. In order to address soil fertility problems, potential synergies can be gained by combining technical options with farmers' knowledge as well as training of farmers and development agent on new soil fertility management approaches. So, the results of this review showed that, the integrated application of organic and inorganic fertilizers improve productivity of crops as well as the fertility status of the soil. The reasons for this are many, which include access or availability of inputs, use of organic resources for other purposes in place of soil fertility, nutrient balancing, collecting, transporting and management of organic inputs and economic returns of investments.</p>
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Soil degradation due to nutrient mining, erosion and desertification is the major threat to food production in dry zone. The reasons for the widespread of these ecological problems have been fairly well documented, but adequate solutions have not yet reached the application phase. The problem of soil fertility in the dry zone like most sub-Saharan African countries is driven by a wide range of biophysical, chemical and socio-economic factors. The first one is the geologic origin of the parent material on which the soils have developed.

The parent materials consist of old and weathered materials, which probably have never contained many nutrient-bearing minerals. The second cause of low fertility is nutrient depletion. Nutrient balances are negative for many cropping systems indicating that farmers are mining their soils. The third factor which indirectly influences restoration of soil fertility in dry zone is the farmers' socio-economic conditions. Macro-economic policies also play a pivotal role in influencing the accessibility, availability and the type of inputs a

farmer can use. Unfavourable exchange rates, poor producer prices, high inflation, poor infrastructure and lack of markets contribute to low fertilizer use by farmers. The major cereal crops grown in dry zone are maize, millet, sorghum and rice. Generally, there was decline in yield of these crops in the last one decade. The particular interest is the lower yield of rice despite government efforts at revamping rice production in the country. This was attributed to farmers' inability to obtain good quality and high yielding seeds (NAERLS, 1999) and shortage in supply of fertilizer during the period. It is apparent that no single measure could be recommended to tackle the problem of soil fertility in dry zone. The technical actions, which are envisaged to enhance and restore soil fertility, have to be selected and designed in accordance with the specific constraints and potentials of these very diverse environments (Dudal, 2002). It is therefore logical that several technological and institutional innovations that can solve soil fertility decline were developed based on specific constraints and potentials.

Physical Environment of Dry Zone (Sub-Saharan Africa)

Climate

Rainfall and particularly the length of the rainy season, has a direct influence on the vegetation of the savanna zones, which ranges from semi-arid and near desert conditions. The total amount, duration and distribution of rainfall, together with solar radiation, are the most important determinants of the types of crops that can be grown. The far north, with less than 700 mm annual rainfall, has millet as the most important cereal crop. In the dry zone, with higher rainfall, sorghum replaces millet. However, there has been a dramatic change in the farming practice and food habits of the people within the dry zone leading to increased maize cultivation and consumption in preference to sorghum (Lombin, 1987). The mean air temperature ranges between 21 and 32°C and permits the production of both the cool season and the warm season crops, the optimal temperatures for which have been given as 15-2 and 30-40°C, respectively (Black, 1971). The dry zone agro-ecological zones are well suited to the production of most tropical cereals and some temperate crops.

Soils

The major soils of the dry zone may be grouped into four descriptive categories and classified according to the USDA (Anonymous, 1975). Surface soil (0-20 cm) samples were collected from 30 different locations across the various agro-ecological zones of the dry zone and analysed for some important physical and chemical properties. The results show that the soils range from sandy loam to loam in texture, moderately acidic in reaction, low in Organic Carbon (OC), available phosphorus, total nitrogen and Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) according to the classification made by (FMNAR, 1990). The data indicate that continuous cultivation of the weakly buffered soils of dry zone will result in a rapid decline of exchangeable cations and soil acidification.

Managing Soil Resources of Dry Zone (Sub-Saharan Africa)

Bush Fallow

Many years ago, farmers in dry zone have realized that continuous food crop production cannot be achieved without restoration of soil fertility. Traditionally, farmers have maintained soil fertility through bush fallow (Van Reuler and Prins, 1993) whereby arable land is allowed to revert to fallow after 3-4 years of continuous cultivation. The fields are abandoned for 7-10 years so that natural vegetation could regrow. During the fallow period, soil fertility could, at least partially, be restored. Mounting demographic pressure and other socio-economic pressures have forced farmers to shorten the fallow period, by increasing the cultivation period. With conversion of shifting cultivation systems to (semi) permanent agriculture, soils no longer have time to recuperate after a period of cropping. The consequence of this development is that the fertility of these soils declines and yields continue to decline also. Therefore, alternative farming systems had to be developed to arrest the declining situation so that there will be enough food for the teeming population.

Improved Land Use Systems

Crop rotation/Intercropping: Legumes have long been recognized as an important component of

cropping systems in the dry zone of grain legumes with cereal crops is a common feature. The crop combinations and planting arrangements are infinitely variable and range from mixed cropping, in which many species are sown randomly in a field, to stricter row or strip intercropping (Francis, 1986). Although intercrops can produce greater yields than sole cropping, they generally do so by extracting more nutrients from the soil than sole crops (Dalal, 1974 and Mason *et al.*, 1986) and may therefore cause more rapid decline in soil fertility. Cereal/legume rotations rather than mono-cropping have been suggested as an effective means to increase soil productivity. In addition to improving soil physical and chemical properties, legume-based rotations may also decrease pest and disease incidence and addition of growth promoting substances (Giller, 2001).

Although the potential of legumes in improving soil fertility is clear, the actual contributions to many cropping systems are surprisingly variable. Yields of maize grown after soybean on an Alfisol were increased from 2.5 to 4.0 t ha⁻¹, compared with only 1.8 t ha⁻¹ in continuous cropping, where all the legume Stover had been removed (Kasasa *et al.*, 1999). Bala *et al.* (2003) recorded maize grain yield of only 600 kg ha⁻¹ with post-soybean 40 kg N ha⁻¹ application when all aboveground residues, except litter falling from leaves before harvest were exported from the fields following the present farmer practice. When the area of land sown to legumes is taken into account, estimate for inputs from N₂-fixation come to less than 5 kg N ha⁻¹ year⁻¹ for cropped land in most cases (Giller *et al.*, 2000). Thus, the amounts of organic residues available in most cropping systems limit their role in maintaining soil fertility.

Green Manures

In contrast to the economic role of grain legumes, a green manure legume is grown wholly for use as a source of organic manure for a subsequent crop. This obviously maximizes the amount of N from the legume available for the next crop. Green manure legumes usually contain adequate N to promote mineralization shortly after soil incorporation. Examples are *Crotolaria*, *Mucuna* and *Sesbania* species, where research has indicated that over 100 kg N ha⁻¹ was accumulated in the above-ground plant parts under favourable

soil and climatic conditions (Giller and Wilson, 1991). Juo and Kang (1989), assessed the performance of *Mucuna* and *Pueraria* as green manures in rotation with maize and found that maize yields were maintained at 2-3 t ha⁻¹ over at least 10 years without fertilizer application. Although it has been consistently demonstrated that soil fertility and crop yield could be effectively maintained in this way (Carsky *et al.*, 1999), its acceptance by the peasant farmers was hampered by the tedium of land preparation with native hoes and the economics of the practice. It was not an easy problem convincing a farmer to adopt a system that includes unproductive fallow.

Organic Sources of Nutrients

Organic resources not only supply many nutrients for crop production including micronutrients but are also a valuable source of Soil Organic Matter (SOM). Increasing the SOM content improves soil structure or tilth, increases the water holding capacity of coarse-textured sandy soils, improves drainage in fine-textured clay soils, provides a source of slow release nutrients, reduces wind and water erosion and promotes growth of earthworms and other beneficial organisms. SOM also contributes to greater efficiency of fertilizer use (Dudal and Roy, 1995, Rosen, 2003). A comprehensive literature on this subject is available (Karikari and Yayock, 1987, Tarfa and Iwuafor, 2002). Significantly high crop yields were obtained in both short and long-term with the application of increasing rate of farmyard manure. The yield obtained was similar to that obtained with the application of inorganic fertilizer. The organic component of the mixture may give additional benefits in the longer term.

Mineral Soil Amendments

Phosphate rock: Next to N, P is the most limiting nutrient to crop production in dry zone. However, the region is endowed with deposits of Phosphate Rock (PR) which can serve both a sustainability goal (restoring the P stock of the soils) and a productive goal (immediate yield increases). A lot of research has been conducted within the sub-region to devise ways of using this natural resource with maximum efficiency and at minimum cost, for the benefit of resource-poor farmers.

The use of PR for direct application has been subject to much controversy (Khasawneh and Doll, 1978). Greenhouse and field studies in several locations in dry zone showed that Crystalizer Super Fertilizer (Blend of Sokoto PR + Magnesite) could be a viable alternative to the soluble P fertilizers (Yusuf *et al.*, 2003). The main disadvantages of directly applied PR are lack of immediate agronomic value on non-acid soils and difficulties in handling and transporting. Despite these disadvantages, it is believed that direct application of PR is an important part of an integrated natural resource management strategy, as the fundamental factors affecting the agronomic efficiencies of this natural resource become well understood (Lyasse *et al.*, 2002). Research at IITA showed that certain herbaceous or grain legumes are able to utilize P from PR due to rhizosphere processes enhancing the P availability (Lyasse *et al.*, 2002). The replenishment of soil P through PR in combination with judicious field management practices to overcome other nutrient limitations and crop growth constraints, would provide benefits of increased crop production and income to farmers, as well as certain environmental benefits (Izac, 1997).

Mineral Fertilizers

History of Fertilizer Use in Dry Zone

The first indication on the potential value of mineral fertilizers in dry zone was given by (Hartley, 1937) who reported the response of cereals to small application of farmyard manure and showed that these responses were very well matched by the responses to application of super phosphate containing quantities of phosphate equivalent to that in the farmyard manure. This work continued until 1939, when he showed that aside from cereals, groundnuts also gave good responses to application of super phosphate. The scope of fertilizer investigations expanded from 1952 onward to cover all the major crops in the region. Early trials undertaken indicated economic responses to only N and P (Greenwood, 1951, Obi, 1959), therefore most fertilizer programmes in the region have been confined to these two main limiting nutrients. In 1962-63, areas of different responses were identified with the Northern part delineated as areas of high response to P while the Southern part was observed to show high response to N.

Continuous cultivation and introduction of high yielding varieties have led to accelerated exploitation of the soil so that; potassium which was hitherto considered adequately supplied in the soils has also become a problem. In 1965, requirements of N and P were passed to the Ministry of Agriculture and the use of compound fertilizers was recommended. Some evidence of deficiencies of boron, Zn and manganese has recently been reported, with indications that the deficiencies will spread rather quickly with intensive and continuous cropping (Chude, 1998). In nutrient terms, fertilizer consumption decreased consistently between 1995 and 2000 following. From year 2000, however, there had been a noticeable upward trend in fertilizer consumption to date.

Crop Response to Mineral Fertilizer in Dry Zone

The effect of fertilizers on crop yield can only be understood fully by studying the results of field experiments that test increasing dressing of each nutrient and also show how the nutrient use together interact to build up yield (Mokwunye, 1990). In a 3³ factorial experiment using N at 0, 90 and 180 kg ha⁻¹ and 0, 45 and 90 kg ha⁻¹ each of P and K, a mean grain yield of 4059 kg ha⁻¹ for all the 27 treatment combinations was obtained in the dry zone (Yusuf, 2003). Yield increases of 94.8 and 179.3% were obtained at 90 and 180 kg N ha⁻¹, respectively. Yaro *et al.* (2003) also observed increase in maize yield with application of mineral fertilizer. Goldsworthy (1967) reported that 18 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ and 26 kg N ha⁻¹ were most economic rates of phosphate and nitrogen fertilizers respectively for sorghum in the dry zone. Heathcote (1972) has also reported significant responses of maize to. These results were obtained from short-term trials. However, in long-term trials, yields generally decreased after several years despite fertilizer application.

The limiting factors might be other nutrients not included in the fertilizer formulation (e.g., micronutrients), distortion in soil physical, chemical and biological conditions. In addition to yield decrease, continuous cropping and fertilization with inorganic fertilizers have impaired many soil properties in the dry zone. Reduced cation exchange capacity, exchangeable cations and upset in the cationic balance have been reported by (Agbenin and Goladi, 1997).

For farmers to maintain high yields and improve soil fertility under intensive, continuous cultivation, they have to rely on alternative sources of nutrients that will be affordable, accessible, sourced locally or generated within the farm.

Integrated Nutrient Management: Combined Use of Organic and Mineral Fertilizers

In recent years, the focus of soil fertility research has been shifted towards the combined application of organic resources and fertilizers as a way to arrest the ongoing soil fertility decline in Saharan Africa (Vanlauwe *et al.*, 2001). This is simply because experience has shown that the most rewarding benefits occur when different technologies are combined. When applying organic resources and mineral fertilizer simultaneously, one hardly ever observes negative interactions, indicating that even without clearly understanding the mechanisms underlying positive interactions, applying organic resources in combination with mineral inputs stands as an appropriate fertility management principle.

Several authors working in dry zone have demonstrated the benefits of complementary use of mineral fertilizers and manures (Yaro *et al.*, 2003, Tarfa *et al.*, 2001). Jones (1971) found that, in the absence of fertilizers, it required at least the application of 7.5 t ha⁻¹ of manure to measure an increase in soil C and N. When fertilizers were added, the manure rate dropped to 5.0 t ha⁻¹. In the same location (Hartley, 1937) observed no significant difference in seed cotton and sorghum grain yield with the application of fertilizer and 2.25 t FYM ha⁻¹ compared to double the rate of the fertilizer.

Recently (Iwuafor *et al.*, 2002) reported a similar trend in maize yield on farmer-managed demonstration trials in the NGS of dry zone. An ideal combination of organic and mineral fertilizers does not exist. The optimum combination depends on the targets and the situation of the particular farm. The major constraint to use of FYM is the large quantities required to satisfy crop need. For example, 100 kg of 10-0-10 fertilizer contains about the same amount of N-P-K as 2,000 kg of FYM. Thus FYM needs to be applied at very high rates to make up for their low nutrient content and to supply enough humus to improve the soil physical condition.

Even then, availability of the nutrients to plants depends on the handling method used to conserve and store the manure before field application. Tremendous nutrient losses due to volatilization and leaching are encountered during storage and application if FYM are not properly handled. The targets refer to the levels of SOM and yield that are attainable within the managerial and economical constraints of the farm.

The Way Forward: Integrated Soil Fertility Management

Despite diversity of approaches and solutions and the investment of time and resources by a wide range of institutions as enumerated above, soil fertility degradation continues to prove to be a substantially intransigent problem and as the single most important constraint to food security in the African continent (Sanchez and Leakey, 1997). Return to investment in soil fertility has not been commensurate to research outputs (AHI, 1997). Farmers are only likely to adopt sound soil management if they are assured of return on their investment. Integrated Soil Fertility Management (ISFM) is now regarded as a strategy that helps low resource endowed farmers mitigate many problems and the characteristics of poverty and food insecurity by improving the quantity and quality of food, income and resilience of soil productive capacity (Kimani *et al.*, 2001).

ISFM is the adoption of a systematic conscious participatory and broad knowledge intensive holistic approach to research on soil fertility that embraces the full range of driving factors and consequences such as biological, physical, chemical, social, economic and political aspects of soil fertility degradation. The approach advocates for among others, careful management of soil fertility aspects that optimize production potentials through incorporation of a wide range of adoptable soil management principles, practices and options productive and sustainable agro-ecosystems.

Sustainable Agro-Ecosystems and Returns of Investments

Ecosystem approaches and ecosystem health are new ideas that are transforming the traditional sectoral and disciplinary approach to agriculture, land management and human development.

The agro-ecosystems specialist group promotes sustainable agricultural practices and agrobiodiversity management under changing climatic conditions and encourages ecosystem-based approaches and resource conservation technologies for transforming agriculture as a sustainable enterprise. The challenges are greater in developing countries, due to the added constraint of resources. Agriculture constitutes the main activity in terms of use of natural resources, and generation of employment in developing countries. It contributes significantly to the livelihood of the poorest sectors of society. It allows the production of food that if accessible and available in adequate quantity and quality could contribute to the overall health and nutrition of the human population.

An agro-ecosystem is a conceptual construct used to describe a geographically and functionally coherent domain of agricultural activity. It includes all living and non-living components and the interactions among them'. Researchers often consider the farm as the basic unit of an agro-ecosystem, but this concept may not be relevant in extensive grazing systems. The precise geographic scale can vary from a system involving a single farm to communities and watersheds composed of many farms and even beyond that to large eco-regions.

The definition is context-specific, and in each case, it is somewhat arbitrary. Regardless of the scale, agro-ecosystems are not closed systems. It is normal that agro-ecosystems are characterized by driving variables or inputs that include immigration and inflows of capital, information, energy, fertilizers, chemicals, and human infrastructure and knowledge. Natural driving variables or inputs include solar radiation, rain, wind and water. Most agro-ecosystems also experience losses or outflows from the system such as water, and emigration. Nutrient losses caused by leaching and the export of crops and livestock are common.

Agro-ecosystems cover 30% of the world's land area. Farmers manage more land area than any other group of people. During the last 50 years, scientific progress (the green revolution) in plant and animal breeding, irrigation, pest and disease control, labour saving technologies, and food processing enabled food production to keep pace with the demands of a growing human population. Without these technological breakthroughs and compared to 1961, three times more land in China and the United States and two times more in India

would have to be under cultivation in order to achieve the food production levels obtained in 1995. To meet the demand caused by the continuing increase in population and the increasing demand for animal products in the developing countries, food production must double over the next 30 years. Agriculture now faces the tasks of further enhancing food production while simultaneously reversing soil degradation, replenishing soil capital, and overcoming the harmful effects of agricultural chemicals. Degraded agro-ecosystems are less resilient to stresses caused by global variation and climatic changes. They are sites where there is growing concern about the projected increase in risks to human health. One consequence has been the rise of a more holistic agro-ecosystem view of agriculture as the paradigm for understanding sustainable production.

This approach is being tested in a joint project between the Institute for Agricultural Research in some dry African countries and the International Fertilizer Development Centre (IFDC-Africa Division) in some selected villages in dry zone. The project which started in the year 2000 with less than 100 farmers in 6 farmers' groups now has a membership of over 3000 with 50 registered farmers' associations. The technology being used on the acid soils of the project site coupled with adoption of improved crop planting pattern of soybean/maize or soybean/sorghum in ratio 4:2. This was compared with farmers practice (FP) of intercropping soybean with maize or sorghum. The crops are rotated in the following year thus providing two crops for the farmers in the same year and residual N and other rotation benefits are utilized in the following year. In the second year of the project crop residues are either incorporated in the field or fed to livestock and the manure is returned to the field.

The farmers have been linked to agro-processing companies and other government agencies who buy surplus of their produce at prices relatively above the current market price. The paradigm embraces the full range of multiple purpose options (MPOs) and driving factors and consequences of soil degradation in different farming systems and land types.

Conclusion

This research has demonstrated that a wide range of technologies is available for soil fertility improvement in Dry Zone (Saharan Africa). However, wide scale adoption of these technologies has been hampered by unfavourable socio-economic and political conditions. The lack of economic motivation, the scarcity of markets to sell a surplus and the paucity of credit facilities have been major constraints to improved soil fertility in dry zone. There is no comprehensive, integrated rural development programme that looks at the entire farm as a system comprising other subsystems. Most of the recommendations are plot-based and do not consider within farm variability. A complete redress of soil fertility decline in dry zone cannot be achieved without commitments from State and National governments. Government should articulate the views and concerns of all stakeholders; identify gaps in knowledge and information and outline processes to fill them.

The ISFM is a new research approach that seeks to overcome the shortcomings of the past conventional approaches. It links the development of resource conserving technologies, support to institutions and farmer groups and provision of enabling policy environment for agricultural investment. The approach advocates for participatory farmers research; a holistic approach to address many and complex farming systems problems so as to achieve wide validity and adoption of agro-ecosystems that operate with dynamic natural and economic environment.

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